

A STUDY ON THERMO-OXIDATIVE STABILITY OF NON-MDA PMR POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Two kinds of diamine monomers, BAPP and BABE, were used in PMR polyimides instead of MDA to develop NON-MDA polyimide systems. Thermo-oxidative stability and elevated-temperature mechanical properties of graphite fiber reinforced NON-MDA polyimide composites were evaluated to be compared with PMR-15 composite. The results showed that the NON-MDA polyimide composites have similar mechanical properties and thermo-oxidative stability to that of PMR-15 composite, thus BAPP and BABE have the potentiality of replacing MDA to be used in PMR polyimide composites.

KEYWORDS: PMR polyimide composite, thermo-oxidative stability, mechanical property

INTRODUCTION

The in-situ of polymerization of monomer reactants(PMR) polyimide resins which first developed at the NASA Lewis Research Center [1] have been used in aircraft engines for its high temperature mechanical properties and processability [2]. PMR-15 is of the best known PMR polyimide synthesized from three monomers, MDA, NE and BTDE. PMR-15 has a number of unique performances, including easy processing, good mechanical properties, excellent retention of mechanical properties at elevated temperatures (288 ~ 316°C) [3], however, its notable shortcomings are inadequate resin flow for complicated composite structures' fabrication and a suspected carcinogen from the use of MDA [4], so it is severely limited in the applications.

The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of replacing the MDA monomer in PMR-15 with other two aromatic diamine monomers BAPP and BABE on composite high-temperature mechanical properties and thermo-oxidative stability.

EXPERIMENTAL

The monomers used in this study are shown in table 1. The BTDE/NE was prepared by refluxing a suspension of BTDA/NA in anhydrous ethyl until the BTDA/NA dissolved and then continued heating at the reflux temperature for an additional two hours to result to a 50 wt% BTDE/NE ethyl solution. The PMR resin solutions were prepared at room temperature by adding the diamine monomers(MDA, BAPP, or BABE) to the BTDE/NE solution to maintain 50 wt% solids. All of the resin formulated molecular weights are about 1500.

AS4 graphite fiber prepreg tapes were made by solution impregnation, which calculated to give composites having approximately 60 vol% fiber. The tapes were cut into 26 cm by 18 cm

plies and stacked unidirectional 16 plies thick. The stack was placed into a matched metal die and cured on a hot molding press, figure 1 showed the cure cycle. 1.5 MPa pressures were used for NON-MDA systems: LP-15(BAPP) and LF-15(BABE), and 2.5 MPa pressures for PMR-15. The postcures were carried out in the air circulating oven at 330 for 16 hours.

Table 1- Monomers used for polyimide synthesis

Structure	Name	Abbreviation
	monomethyl ester of endo-5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid	NE
	dimethyl ester of 3,3'-4,4'-benzophenonetetracarboxylic acid	BTDE
	4,4'-methylenedianiline	MDA
	2,2'-bis(4-aminophenoxyphenyl)-propane	BAPP
	4,4'-bis(aminobenzoyl)diphen-ether	BABE

Fig.1: Cure cycle used for laminate processing.

Isothermal exposure of the specimens was performed in air circulating oven. Flexural and interlaminar shear tests were carried out before and after exposure to 260, 280 and 300. Flexural strength tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D-790, interlaminar shear strength tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D-2344. Elevated temperature tests were conducted in an environmental heating chamber following at the test temperature. Composite weight loss measurements were performed after exposure to 260, 280 and 300. Glass transition temperatures (T_g) were determined by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The composite weight loss characteristics after exposure in air at 260, 280 and 300 are shown in Fig. 2. It is seen that all systems have a similar weight loss for exposure to air at 260 and 280 beyond 300 hours. After 1000 hours of exposure, LP-15 and LF-15 composites have higher weight loss (1.27wt% at 260 and 2.25wt% at 280) than that of PMR-15 (1.06wt% at 260 and 1.34wt% at 280), and there is still not apparent difference between LP-15, LF-15, and PMR-15 composites.

Fig.2: Weight loss of the composites with aging time at 260, 280 and 300.

Fig. 3 showed the mechanical property retention of the composites after 1000 hours aging tests at different temperatures. We can see that after exposure 1000 hours at 260 and 280, the interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength retention of all systems are higher than 90%; but after exposure 1000 hours at 300, the retention of interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength of LP-15 and LF-15 composites is much lower than that of PMR-15 composite. thus LP-15 and LF-15 composites have a similar thermo-oxidative stability to that of PMR-15 composite up to 280.

Fig.3: The FS(a) and ILSS(b) of composites after 1000 hr. aging at 260, 280 and 300°C.

Fig.4: FS(a) and ILSS(b) of the composites at different temperatures.

Fig.5: Variation of 280ILSS(a) and FS(b) of the composites with exposing time at 280.

Fig. 4 showed the mechanical properties of LP-15, LF-15, and PMR-15 composites at room temperature, 260, 280 and 300. The LP-15 and LF-15 composites exhibit the high room temperature flexural strength and 260 interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength retention values, and at 280 the interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength retention are still higher than 60% and 55% respectively. But at 300 the LP-15 and LF-15 composites have a lower property retention, this can be attributed to their lower Tg(LP-15: 318; LF-15: 332 and PMR-15: 343). Fig. 5 showed the variation of interlaminar shear strength and flexural

strength characteristics of the composites after exposure and tested in air at 280. The results exhibit that the flexural properties at 280 of LF-15 and LP-15 composites are similar to that of PMR-15 composites. After 1000 hours of exposure to air at 280, all systems have a very high flexural strength retention (>85%), the LP-15 composite exhibits lower interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength retention, but PMR-15 shows the best interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength retention characteristics.

CONCLUSIONS

LP-15 and LF-15 have similar mechanical properties, and thermo-oxidative stability to that of PMR-15 and offer excellent potential as PMR-15 replacements for use at temperatures up to 280. Thus BAPP and BABE have the potentiality of replacing MDA to be used in PMR polyimide composites.

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